

A multidimensional investigation of covert contrast in Swedish acquiring children’s speech – a project description

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Abstract

This paper provides a description of a current PhD project in phonetics at the Department of Linguistics at Stockholm University. A short background is provided, the intended experiments are presented and the potential contributions of the results are outlined.

Introduction

Covert contrasts “... involve sounds that the child produces differently (acoustically or articulatorily) but are heard and transcribed by listeners with the same phonetic symbol.” (Gibbon & Lee, 2017b, p. 1). Covert contrast is, in other words, a systematic and measurable contrast between two speech sounds that is neutralized in the ears of the listener. Covert contrast has been found in children’s production of speech sounds that vary in voicing (Macken & Barton, 1980), place (Munson, Edwards, Schellinger, Beckman, & Meyer, 2010) and manner of articulation (Tyler, 1995). Previous studies have uncovered covert contrast in child speech through articulatory imaging (e.g. electropalatography, see Gibbon & Lee, 2017a) and perceptual judgements (e.g. Munson et al., 2010), although most have performed acoustic analyses (e.g. Forrest, Weismer, Hodge, Dinnsen, & Elbert, 2009; Tyler, Figurski, & Langsdale, 1993). However, there is evidence that children manipulate a range of phonetic and/or articulatory parameters in the production of covert contrasts (Gibbon

& Lee, 2017a). As such, predetermining which acoustic parameters to explore in acoustic analyses is difficult, and may “miss the mark” (Gibbon & Lee, 2017b). Therein lies the advantage of perceptual judgements – they are sensitive to (potential) covert contrasts irrespective of what phonetic cues are manipulated (Gibbon & Lee, 2017b).

The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) has been used in many previous studies that have utilized perceptual evaluations in the search of covert contrast (e.g. Munson et al., 2010; Strömbergsson, Salvi, & House, 2015). VAS is a continuous scale consisting of a 100 mm line with two endpoints, (for example two speech sounds, see Figure 1). Given this continuous measure, adults are able to perceive fine phonetic detail in child speech (Strömbergsson et al., 2015), which would have gone unnoticed in transcription analyses (Gibbon & Lee, 2017b; Munson et al., 2010).

Figure 1. An example of a VAS in a digital interface, with speech sounds /t/ and /k/ as endpoints. Figure reproduced from Strömbergsson (2014) with the author’s permission.

To date, only one study has been conducted with Swedish speaking children (Strömbergsson et al., 2015) and therefore an exploration of fine phonetic variation in the speech of children acquiring Swedish is of great interest.

Speech Sound Disorder

Speech sound disorder (SSD) is the most common paediatric communication impairment and constitutes a vast proportion of speech-language pathologist's caseload (McLeod & Baker, 2014). SSD is an umbrella term that encompasses developmental difficulties with production, perception and/or phonological representations of speech sounds (International Expert Panel on Multilingual Children's Speech, 2012). As such, the term SSD encompasses a large and heterogeneous group of children with varying degrees and forms of difficulties.

In Sweden, idiopathic SSDs (i.e. SSDs of unknown aetiology) have traditionally been described as phonological language disorder (*fonologisk språkstörning*) or articulation disorder (*artikulationsstörning*) (Nettelblatt, 1983). This classification reflects a viewpoint that differentiates between phonological ability (as part of language ability) and articulation (speech motor control) (Strömbergsson, 2014). The shortcomings in the speech of children with SSDs are often described as phonological processes (e.g. substitutions – when a child substitutes one sound with another from within the given languages phonological system) or as articulatory distortions (e.g. when a child substitutes one sound for an allophone or for a sound from outside the given languages phonological system) (Ball & Müller, 2002).

This (dichotomous) classification of speech sound errors has been criticized (Ball & Müller, 2002), in part due to the fact that the loci of the deficit is inferred by surface errors, without insight into the child's actual phonological

processing, speech perception or -production. Moreover, the occurrence of a covert contrast in a child's apparent substitution challenges the idea of an SSD due to phonological deficits – covert contrast *de facto* involves a systematic distinction between the two target sounds, even though the listener does not perceive it. As children who produce covert contrast have been found to progress faster in speech-language therapy than children who produce true substitutions (Tyler et al., 1993), investigating the occurrence of covert contrast in the speech of children with SSD is of clinical importance.

Stopping is one of the most common substitutions in Swedish acquiring children (Nettelblatt & Salameh, 2007) and involves the production of a stop consonant for a fricative (e.g. [t] for /s/). To the best of our knowledge only one previous study has explored covert contrast in the stopping of /s/, in the speech of three children with SSD (phonological impairment) (see Tyler, 1995). Tyler (1995) found evidence of an acoustic distinction between the targets /s/ and /t/ for one of the three participating children. However, the study only used durational measures (Voice Onset Time, VOT) in the acoustic analysis, thus missing potential contrast conveyed through spectral parameters. Moreover, a substantially larger sample is needed to draw any conclusions about the prevalence and nature of covert contrast in this apparent substitution. Hence, exploring stopping of /s/ in detail would provide a valuable contribution to the current state of knowledge.

Description of misarticulated speech

Phonetic transcription is a valuable and well-used tool in the description of children's speech (Munson et al., 2010). However, transcription is typically based on a limited set of symbols that are modelled after adult speech production. Therefore, transcription analyses have limited capabilities when it comes to

capturing fine phonetic variation in child speech, such as covert contrast (Gibbon & Lee, 2017a; Munson et al., 2010).

In the clinical care of children with SSD, description of speech is important for diagnosis, choice of intervention as well as for the monitoring of progress in therapy (e.g. Munson, Schellinger, & Carlson, 2012). Munson et al. (2012) propagate the importance of fine-grained methods of analysis and suggest clinical use of VAS. However, one issue regarding the clinical application of VAS is that previous VAS studies have utilized isolated syllables of child speech as auditory stimuli (e.g. Munson et al., 2010; Strömbergsson et al., 2015), while clinical speech assessments typically elicit whole-word productions (McLeod & Verdon, 2014). As words include more information that could potentially bias adult's perceptual judgements of speech, compared to syllables (see e.g. Ganong, 1980), it is conceivable that whole-word stimuli will affect the gradience of ratings of speech sounds with VAS.

Speech perception and phonological awareness in children with SSD

Over and above difficulties with speech production, children with SSD also exhibit difficulties in speech perception (Njiland, 2009) and have an increased risk of deficits in phonological awareness (Rvachew & Grawburg, 2006). However, there is a large variation in research findings regarding these abilities, and the relationship between production and perception in children with SSD is not yet clear. An ongoing survey of Swedish speech-language pathologists (110 answers, Wikse Barrow, ongoing) shows that all clinicians do not systematically assess speech perception (49% always/often do so) and phonological awareness (39% always/often do so) in preschool children with suspected SSD. As such investigating the relationship between these abilities is important and could in the long term contribute to the

creation of national practice guidelines for assessment and intervention for children with SSD.

PhD project

The present doctoral thesis project is in its initial stage, and the defence is planned to take place in the spring of 2023. The project intends to explore acoustic and perceptual features of fine phonetic variation in child speech through three experimental studies. An ethical permit application has been submitted to the Swedish Ethical Review Authority (registration number 2019-02854).

The first two studies of the project will focus on the exploration of covert contrast in the stopping of /s/. The first study will analyse children's successful and misarticulated productions of intended /s/, through acoustic analyses and perceptual judgements by naïve adult listeners using VAS. The second study will explore whether adult ratings of children's speech are influenced by the context in which the sound is presented (syllable or word).

The third and final study will delve into the relationship between children's speech production and – perception. The results will be related to detailed profiles of the children's phonological processing abilities as well as adult ratings of their speech production.

Materials and methods

The first two studies will utilize a VAS in a digital interface. Each sound will be assigned a transcription category (between /s/ and /t/), following the procedure in (Munson et al., 2010; Strömbergsson et al., 2015) and relevant acoustic parameters will be analysed (e.g. VOT, spectral centre of gravity and duration of noise burst). The location of the VAS ratings will be tallied for each recording, to investigate if ratings correspond to transcription categories and/or acoustic phenomena. Ratings will also be tallied for each individual, to explore

whether respondents use the entire scale and whether they provide reliable ratings.

The third study will use standardized language assessments and study-specific tests to investigate phonological processing and speech production in participating children. The speech perception experiments will use recordings from peers with typical and atypical pronunciations to gauge how the children perceive contrasts that they themselves struggle to produce.

Contributions

We expect the PhD project to contribute the following:

∞ An investigation of an underexplored contrast – as of yet, there is little evidence of covert contrast in the stopping of /s/.

∞ Survey of Swedish speaking children – only one previous study has been conducted with children who are acquiring Swedish.

∞ New insights into the relationship between phonological processing, speech perception and -production in children with and w/o SSD.

∞ An exploration of VAS function given whole-word stimuli. Results from this investigation may provide guidance for the clinical use of VAS.

∞ Fuel for the discussion regarding terminology to describe paediatric SSDs and speech error patterns in Swedish speech-language pathology practice. Results from this project may in the long-term affect 1) description of SSD, 2) choice of intervention and 3) monitoring of progress in intervention.

∞ Foundations for national practice guidelines regarding assessment and intervention for children with SSD.

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